

The Redeemed Christian Church of God

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The Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) was founded in Nigeria in 1952 by Josiah Olufemi Akindayomi. The church has a rich history and a profound impact on the global Christian landscape. Akindayomi was born in Ondo, Southwestern Nigeria, in 1909. Although he was born into a family that followed indigenous religions, he later joined the Anglican Church, where he was baptized in 1927. His religious desire made him move further to the Cherubim and Seraphim Church (C & S) in 1931. He founded a prayer group within the C&S, which he called Egbe Ogo Oluwa (The Glory of God Fellowship) in 1947. It was this group that metamorphosed into the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) in 1952. According to Ogunewu, Akindayomi made several prophetic declarations about the RCCG that have come to fruition. He predicted that the church would spread to all nations of the world and that it would be characterized by mighty miracles and wonders. Akindayomi also foresaw that the RCCG would be at the forefront of a Pentecostal explosion on the African continent. His commitment to prayer, evangelism, and spiritual growth laid the foundation for the church's remarkable growth and influence. By the time of his death in 1980, RCCG had about 40 parishes within Nigeria. Enoch Adejare Adeboye succeeded Akindayomi as the General Overseer in 1981. Before this appointment, he served as the founder's interpreter, demonstrating his close relationship with the church's origins. Born on March 2, 1942, in Ifewara, Osun State, Nigeria, Adeboye hails from a very humble family. He often shares the story of wearing his first shoes at the age of 18. Adeboye went to Ilesha Grammar School in Osun State and started to study mathematics at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Due to the Nigerian Civil War, he completed his first degree in mathematics at the University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo University) in 1967. His academic pursuits continued with a Master's degree in hydrodynamics from the University of Lagos and a Ph.D. in applied mathematics from the same institution. Adeboye joined the RCCG in 1973 and initially served as an interpreter. In 1975, he was ordained as a pastor by Pa. Josiah Akindayomi. By 1981, he had become the General Overseer, leading the church's expansion. The RCCG, which had 40 parishes in Nigeria at the time of his appointment, has now grown to about 198 nations worldwide, with over 9 million worshipers in Nigeria alone. He is considered a preacher of the holiness movement and emphasizes Christian discipleship through local churches. Adeboye's global impact extends beyond Africa, with a great following for the church through various Christian ministries and social efforts. Adeboye's vision includes establishing RCCG branches within walking or driving distance in cities, ensuring accessibility for worshipers. The church emphasizes holiness, discipleship, and obedience to God's Word. RCCG's impact extends beyond Africa, touching lives through ministries and social efforts. In 1990, the RCCG Bible School was founded, nurturing leaders and ministers. The Redemption Camp in Mowe, Lagos, was purchased in 1983, serving as a hub for conferences, retreats, and worship. The Redeemed Christian Fellowship (RCF) for students was established in 1988, fostering spiritual growth among young believers. The church's headquarters, now at 1-5 Redemption Way, Ebute-Metta, Lagos, symbolizes its journey from humble beginnings to global prominence.

Date Range: 1952 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Africa, Europe, North America, South America, Central America, Europe, Middle East, Asia, Australia, New Zealand

Region tags: New Zealand, Europe, Middle East, Nigeria, Global, South Asia, Africa, South America, United Kingdom, North America, Taiwan

RCCG is rapidly spreading around the world. It is represented in about 197 countries and regions worldwide.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

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- Source 2 URL: <https://youtu.be/7TxD3cxUQcc?si=kJhYHsBvV4cCShH>
- Source 2 Description: Daniel Mike-Bamiloye (2023) Enoch: A Biopic of Pastor E.A. Adeboye
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.rccg.org/>
- Source 3 Description: Official Website of The Redeemed Christian Church of God

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.rccg.org/>

– Source 1 Description: This is the official website of The Redeemed Christian Church of God

– Source 1 URL: <https://rccgkristiansand.files.wordpress.com/2014/07/workers-in-training.pdf>

– Source 1 Description: RCCG Workers in Training Manual

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact in the region where this group is found is highly competitive. This is because there are other religious groups seeking to woo the same population which the group targets into their own fold as well. All these groups compete for the same people the RCCG seeks to recruit as members

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: At its beginning, the C & S from which RCCG developed began as an accommodation of African, particularly Yoruba spirituality. Despite modernisation by Adeboye, this sensitivity continued in contemporary RCCG.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The cultural contact in this region is not neutral. Rather, it is competitive but peacefully so in the southern part of the country. This peaceful outlook in the south of Nigeria cannot be extended to the northern part of the country where religious fanatics hide under the cover of another Abrahamic faith to unleash mayhem on Christians who conduct themselves in the most peaceful manner.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there have been reported cases of violent conflicts between religious groups in northern Nigeria.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: There are no records of violent conflicts between the RCCG and groups outside the sample region.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: For those whose parents are members, those children are potential members. They, however, need to go through baptismal classes and rituals to confirm their membership.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: People from other religions such as Islam and African Traditional Religion) and those from other Christian denominations may opt by personal choice to become members. If so, such would need to go through proper membership classes, including baptism.

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: RCCG proselytize for members through class. This was the way 'model' parishes of the church, escalated the membership started in the 1990s. Societal elites were specifically sought for membership. Similarly, students were attracted to the church through Redeemed Christian Ministry, as are fresh graduates through Redeemed Christian Corpers Fellowship.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: Since, membership has to be by personal decision which was openly professed, a potential member must be 'mature'.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Every potential member must be baptised by immersion, after going through training on the beliefs of the church.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Although the group's members hold very important political posts in the government, the church does not have an official political support. For example, the immediate past Vice President (Prof. Yemi Osinbajo) of the country is a Pastor (leader) in the church. The wife of the current President (Mrs Oluremi Tinubu) is also a pastor in the church.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 9000000

Notes: the denomination is organised into parishes, Areas, Provinces and Regions. The average population of a parish is 1000 members.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 4.5

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: Each parish (branch) of the church has a pastor who is in charge of the church administration. The pastor is usually supported in the administration of the church by other pastors, deacons, church workers and members

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Each parish pastor is equal in rank to other parish pastors but parish pastors in a zone, area, region etc are subject to their Area, Zonal and Regional pastors.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The region (Nigeria) has a National Overseer who oversees the affairs of the church in the country. He is in turn responsible to the General Overseer who leads the global assembly of the church

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

- ↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
 - Number of levels [numeric value]: 7

- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
 - Yes

Notes: This is as they are empowered by the supernatural being.

- ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:
 - No

- ↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:
 - Yes

Notes: The group believes that a life of devotion and dedication to the supreme being guarantees access to power for spiritual feats. Such feats include the performance of miracles.

- ↳ Powers are inherited:
 - No

- ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
 - No

- ↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):
 - No

Notes: In this group, the only thing human leaders could do is to pray for and anoint followers in the hope to attain new spiritual heights. This is not automatic though as the devotion and uprightness of the followers is important to attaining the new height.

- ↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:
 - No

Notes: Real spiritual powers are not domesticated in leadership office. The personal spiritual capacity of the one occupying the office is what matters most in the group.

- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes

- ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - Yes

Notes: The current General Overseer of the church was chosen by the late former leader before his death. It is not clear yet what form the succession will take place when it is time to choose the next leader of the church.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
– No

Notes: Though members hold the view that as humans, their leaders are fallible, however, they do not bring charges against their leaders so flippantly.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
– No

Notes: Though other leaders hold the view that as humans, their leaders are fallible, however, they do not bring charges against their leader so flippantly.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: On this, the Church write about its belief, "We believe that the Bible is the written and revealed Will of God. ... All the Bible teachings are holy, what the Bible reveals as the will of God are such that we should accept, and whatever God writes in the Bible and His Law are to remain unchangeable; for the Heavens and Earth may pass away but the Word of God stands forever. Deut. 4:22; Rev. 22:18, 19; Matt. 24:34-38."

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 10

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 9000000

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 50

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 12

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 10

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Except if attendance at the monthly Holy Ghost Service and the annual Holy Ghost Congress are considered pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Each human person is believed to be made by God "of three parts, namely body, soul and spirit".

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: It is expressed thus in the Church's 'Belief': We experience daily the resurrection of the Spirit, all the born-again souls who are passed from death to life – Eph. 6:14; Rom 6:11; John 5:20. As this body is dissolved, immediately we are entering into our Heavenly Home or house not made with hands eternal in the Heavens – I Cor. 5:1-8 There is resurrection of the Body. Jesus taught us plainly that the buried body will be raised up from the tomb at the last day Job 5:28-29. Paul also explained this to us – Acts 24:15; I Cor. 15:22, 42-44; Phil. 3:21; Dan. 12:2. Only Holy people will be at the resurrection those who belong to Jesus when He appears; but the sinners shall resurrect in hell, a place where people whose names are not found in the Lamb's Book – Rev. 20:4-5; John 5:28-29; Rev. 20:12-15."

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the afterlife which her members will be admitted to is in a space above the earth (in the sky). It is the abode of the supreme being, a very massive city of splendour and peace

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: The Church's clergy lead the burial service for the dead,.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: For the masses, yes, the supreme God resides in the sky. But for the elites of the church, the explicit and often affirmation of God's omnipresence usually prevent them from stating that God resides in physical sky.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: The General Overseer, Pastor E.A. Adeboye is somehow regarded as such.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: As Ukah found out in his field research of the RCCG, Adeboye "... is the physical channel of grace and divine ordinance for the church. He is the physical oracle of the divine; he articulates doctrines and initiates orientations. He is the bridge between his followers and God; 'the God we see now'"

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: very just, can become rightly angry and thus punish justly.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of

human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He has knowledge of what will happen after the end of the world, to the world and to everyone in the world. He is aware of every affair, and indeed he controls what goes on in the world.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, God loves and has mercy on humans.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, God becomes angry.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: This is especially so when one prays. God directs and speaks directly to such persons.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Except by some senior clergy

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

Notes: Except they are allowed by the Supreme God.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: If God gives them the grace.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: If God allows them.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: If they are allowed by God.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: When given the knowledge by God.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: If they are allowed and given the knowledge by God.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

Notes: Under the directive of God

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

Notes: By the direction of God.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Notes: If permitted or directed by God

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supernatural beings can exhibit negative emotions against the oppressors of the righteous and powerless.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Notes: Except taboo is taken to be what is regarded as 'sins', for example, sexual promiscuity, drunkenness, etc.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Homosexuality is disallowed.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - No
 - Notes: If there is any ritual that the supernatural being cares about, it is prayers and worship.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - No
 - Notes: Again, if there are rituals that the supreme being cares about, they are, prayers and worship, and paying of tithes and listening to the word of God.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The Church itself is heavily involved in empowering its members economically through diverse programmes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: All other human beings.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: They can only mete out punishment if directed by God

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It is clearly stated in the Belief of the Church, "The Bible teaches us that there is eternal punishment as well as eternal life – Matt. 25:46. The wicked people will be sent to a fiery hell made of sulphur, to be tormented both day and night. The punishment will continue forever and ever – Rev. 14:10-11; Luke. 16:24; Mark 9:43-44.". This is taken from the official website of the Church. <https://www.rccg.org/our-beliefs/>

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
 - Notes: Except the idea of battle is taken as metaphorical. If so, winning in battle against poverty, family curse, lack of promotion, etc, will be a way that God rewards his children.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
 - Notes: If one is in need of these, perhaps as a farmer.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Under the heading, "Divine Healing without Medicine" in the Church's Belief, it is stated, "Healing without medicine is Biblical – Matt. 4:23; Ps. 103:3; Sickness is caused because of the fall of man. The force behind this is Satan – Job 2:1-9; Luke 13:15; Acts 10:3. But JESUS came to destroy the works of the devil – I John 3:8. Christ purchased our soul from the curse of sin. He bore our infirmities and carried our sorrow – Matt. 8:15-17. By His stripes we are healed. Is 53:4-5; Gal. 3:13; I Peter 2:24. Healing without medicine is of the Gospel – Matt. 9:35; Mark 6:10-18. We read that the twelve Apostles and the seventy

disciples combined healing with their Ministry of the Gospel – Luke 9:1-2; Luke 10:1-9. The Lord commanded us to go into the world, just to teach the nations alone, but that we should also heal the sick – Matt. 28:19-20; Mark 10:1, Mark 16:15-18. We could obtain our healing in these four ways: 1. By individual prayer – John 14:13-14 2. By two people (or a group of people) who have agreed to pray by faith – Matt. 18:19-20. 3. By the laying of hands on the head – Mark 16:18; Acts 9:18; Acts 28:8. 4. By the Ministry of the Elders, anointing the sick with prayer of faith – James 5:14-15 Special Notice – Before we can work by healing without medicine, we would have sanctified our life to the doing of the Law – Rom. 6:13, 19; Rom. 12:1; Matt. 16:24; II Cor. 8:5, 15. Many miracles were performed by the Apostles – Acts 9:33-42; Acts 19:11-12; Acts 28:8-9."

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

Notes: The church teaches its members about family planning. Members are encouraged to give birth to the number of children they can cater to.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: However, Jesus Christ is accepted as the Messiah.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The believers have to preach the Gospel to every corner of the earth before Christ can come.
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In the new heaven and new earth, God will be the King, a sort of theocracy.
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - No
 - ↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:
 - Yes
 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: To be 'saved', one must be 'born-again' - believe the doctrines of evangelical/fundamentalist Christianity. One must also live a moral life and worship regularly in church, including paying tithes.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: In the section titled, 'Dedication' or Separation' in the Church's Belief, it is stated, "Dedication is very important for the children of God for the Lord is Holy – John 17:19; I Peter 1:15-16. If we want god [sic] to be our Father, we must separate and dedicate ourselves unto God – II Cor. 6:17-18. God called us unto Holiness – I Thess. 4:7; Rom. 12:1-2."

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: They are linked to God and His will as revealed in the Bible.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: To God, who is usually conceived anthropomorphically.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: In the section titled, 'Due Reverence to Parents and Authorities' in the Church's Belief, it is explicitly stated, "All Christians are to obey the law of the country, obey the government and authority. They should honor their parents and elders. I Peter 2:13-14; Rom 13:1-5; Eph. 6:1-3."

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Rebellion against Church authority is explicitly forbidden, debts is forbidden, members must be moderate in dressing, marriage should be between a man and a woman and proper procedure must be followed should there be divorce or re-marriage.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Marriage is between a man and a woman, and both are expected to be faithful to each other. Divorce is allowed and remarriage is also allowed. Young people are expected to refrain from sex until they get married. However, there is no punishment for violating this rule.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

Notes: The same law on sexual purity is applicable to all, female or male, elite or not.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: The same law on sexual purity is applicable to all, female or male, elite or not.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: There are some special services, such as the Holy Ghost Congress when fasting may be required.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Although it is not mandatory to give one property or the other, it is encouraged, particularly if one wants to be blessed by God. However, giving of tithes of every of salaries, benefits and every other thing one might acquire is required of members.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: There are weekly, monthly and annual programmes which members are encouraged to attend.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: The risks here include giving the whole of one's first salary. fasting for about forty days every year, giving a gift (called 'sowing')

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Some ethical precepts that are explicitly stated in the Beliefs of the Church include: restitution, due reverence to parents and authorities, rebellion against church authority forbidden, debts forbidden, marriage between one man and one woman only, but with 'proper divorce' if needed, and remarriage.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: In fact, members of this Church are highly placed in Nigerian society; they belong to the higher echelon of the society.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 7

Notes: Prayer mainly and Bible Study,

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 2000000

Notes: Annual Holy Ghost Congress and monthly Holy Ghost Service.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 720

Notes: Monthly Holy Ghost services

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: You cannot become a member, particularly a worker, Deacon or pastor without rigorous assessment through different trainings and activities.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The behaviours of the leaders are always assessed before they are promoted.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Congregation services abound in RCCG.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Each Parish is usually refers to as a family

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– Yes

Notes: The members and parishes see themselves as family.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Nigeria

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Different ventures have been established by the Church to empower its members.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As citizens of Nigeria, the members of RCCG can participate in any relief the Government of Nigeria provides.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: RCCG has many nursery, primary and secondary schools around Nigeria. In addition, it has a

University, the Redeemer's University for the Nation (RUN), which is located in Ede, Osun state Nigeria. RCCG also has some Business or Professional Schools in Lagos.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Apart from the denomination's own, members of RCCG are free to attend other State, Federal or private educational institutions,

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The lowest of the ones that members interact with most is the Home Fellowships. Above that, however, are Parishes, Areas, Zones, Provinces and Regions, in ascending order. The overall office is the Office of the General Overseer at Ebute Metta, Lagos.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Indeed, many of the members, particularly those of the Model parishes belong to the Government's bureaucracy. Apart from this, members may find other things that may require interacting with other bureaucracies, particularly the government's won at the Local, State and Federal levels.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: This is done in the Redemption Camp, the International Headquarters of the Church. Many services, such as the Holy Ghost Services and Holy Ghost Congress are also held in the Redemption Camp. It should also be mentioned, that many members, particularly staff are residing in the Redemption Camp. The Camp is a city in itself.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is done in other parts of Nigeria, apart from the Redemption Camp.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Tithes, gifts, offerings and donations are encouraged for members. According to an interviewee of Ukah (2003), Offerings and tithes "must be paid on every income e. g. salary, profit from business transactions, gifts, etc." The church's Constitution also specifies that members of the church "are expected to give tithes of their income towards the general purposes of the church"

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Nigerian Government levy taxes, particularly on the properties of the Church. The Church leaders also encourage its members and institutions to pay all taxes.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: In the Redemption Camp, the Church has Redemption Guard (RG) which provides security in addition to some hired and armed guards who patrol the perimeters of the camp bordering undeveloped forests. On the RG, Ukah (2003) wrote, "The RG is a squad of trained security personnel from the church which maintains physical security of the Camp all through the day and night. State security officials who happen also to be members of the church such as serving and retired military and police officers train the members of RG. Equipped with modern security and communications gadgets, the RG provides security details for Adeboye in and outside the Camp, except when he travels outside the country. At every corner of the Camp, there are security personnel, all carrying communications equipment such as walkie-talkies. During mass events, they get assistance from the state Police Force and Federal Roads Safety Corps in maintaining traffic discipline and order in and around the Camp, especially along the express road and around the many car parking lots. An Assistant Commissioner of Police, who is also an assistant pastor of the church, Femi Akintemi, acts as a bridge between the church and the state security team that consolidates on the efforts of the crop of

church guards." This was between 2001 and 2002. There has been some other improvement in the Camp since then.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents/members interact with the Nigerian Government' won judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Imprisonment.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The Church has a Constitution and a Memorandum of Association.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members are subject to Nigerian Constitution.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members are free to join the national military.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Nigerian military protect RCCG members because they are also Nigerians.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English and Yoruba are the primary languages. However, all Nigerian languages are used, depending on the location of each local parish.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: English and any Nigerian language (or even human language) can be used.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group only have a liturgical calendar. In this, the popular Gregorian calendar is used to fix the dates of different programmes of the Church.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Church uses the Gregorian Calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Fishing
- Patoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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